

Impact of Inspiratory and Peripheral Muscle Training in Cases with COPD: A Prospective Observational Study

K. Prasanna Kumar Reddy¹, Sreelekha Kotte²

¹Associate Professor, Department of Pulmonary Medicine, MNR Medical College and Hospital, Sangareddy, Telangana, India

²Post Graduate, Final Year, Department of Pulmonary Medicine, MNR Medical College and Hospital, Sangareddy, Telangana, India

Received: 02-01-2023 / Revised: 30-01-2023 / Accepted: 20-02-2023

Corresponding author: Dr Sreelekha Kotte

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Introduction: Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is characterized by continual respiratory symptoms and controlled airflow in the respiratory tracts. Breathing exercises can rehabilitate the lung function in COPD including continuous training of breathing patterns and exercises to respiratory muscles. The present study was designed to assess the role of inspiratory muscle training and peripheral muscle training in pulmonary function and exercises capacity progression in cases with COPD.

Materials and Methods: A source of 80 cases with symptoms and spirometry suggestive of moderate to severe COPD patients above 30 years were recruited. Participants were randomly divided into group IMT (n=40) undergone inspiratory muscle training and group PMT (n=40) undergone peripheral muscle training. At the baseline and end of the session quality of life by COPD assessment test score, mRC dyspnea scores, exercise capacity by 6 minutes walking distance and lung function by Forced Expiratory Volume in one second (FEV₁) were assessed.

Results: The COPD assessment test score was 24 and 17 in group IMT and 22 and 16 in group PMT at baseline and after sessions respectively (p<0.05). The mean 6 minutes walking distance showed increase from baseline to end of sessions. The mean FEV₁ was 50±8.98 and 51±9.18 in group IMT and 45.8±7.88 and 46.5±7.67 in group PMT.

Conclusion: IMT was an effective method to improve the inspiratory muscle strength, pulmonary function, quality of life and without changes in the dyspnea in cases with COPD. Similar outcome was found in terms of peripheral muscle training.

Keywords: COPD, Inspiratory Muscle Training, Lung Function, Quality Of Life.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

COPD is a major public health concern and becoming a leading cause of morbidity and mortality [1]. The severity and recurrence of exacerbation can influence the disease prognosis in COPD. Weakness of respiratory muscles is commonly associated and

contributes to dyspnoea, hypercapnia, decreased SPO₂ in sleep and reduced walking distance [2,3]. Dyspnoea is prominently limiting the body activity thus leads to non-adherence and chronic avoidance of physical exercises. Neglect

physical activities for prolonged duration contribute skeletal muscle deconditioning and reduced ability of exercise capacity which affect the quality of life [4,5].

Exercise and inspiratory muscle training are the management choices to reduce dyspnoea and improve inspiratory muscle strength (IMT), which enhances the quality of life [6]. IMT is effective in associated with pulmonary rehabilitation programs. However, there is literature lack in this context and its effect on dyspnoea [7]. Pulmonary rehabilitation consists of multiple components including cessation of smoking, education, psychosocial support, respiratory exercise practice, vaccination, oxygen support. Outcome can be assessed by measuring functional exercise capacity, severity of dyspnoea, and laboratory measures of exercise performance [8]. With above reference, the present was designed to assess the role of inspiratory muscle training and peripheral muscle training in pulmonary function and exercises capacity progression in cases with COPD.

Materials and Methods

The present Prospective study was conducted in the department of Pulmonary Medicine at MNR Medical College and Hospital from September 2021 to November 2022. A source of 80 cases with symptoms and spirometry suggestive of moderate to severe COPD patients were recruited. The cases symptoms of COPD including chronic cough, chronic sputum and progressive shortness of breath, history of risk factors of COPD including smoking, high exposure to dust and pollution, congenital abnormalities, predisposing genetic factors and spirometry findings including $FEV_1/FVC < 0.7$ and post bronchodilator $FEV_1 < 80\%$ and willing to participate were included. Cases with severe hypertension, respiratory failure,

cardiovascular complication, unstable angina, hemoptysis and not willing to participate were excluded. Written informed consent was obtained from all the cases and study protocol was approved by institutional ethics committee.

Study participants were randomly divided into two groups. Group IMT consists 40 participants undergone inspiratory muscle training and group PMT consists 40 participants undergone peripheral muscle training. Detailed history was collected and study participants were subjected to detailed clinical examination. The inspiratory muscle training (IMT) was conducted by using inspiratory muscle device. Participants were advised to inspire and expire air for 2 min with one-minute intermittent rest over the period of 20 minutes for 20 sessions. The peripheral muscle training was conducted by using elastic resistance bands with progressive increase in force. Elastic band resistance exercises were conducted for 20 min in two sets with intermittent rest of two minutes for 20 sessions.

The quality of life of participants were assessed by measuring BMI, COPD assessment test score, mRC dyspnea scores. The exercise capacity was assessed by levels of SPO₂ and 6 minutes walking distance. The lung function was assessed by Forced Expiratory Volume in one second (FEV_1). The scores of above parameters were measured at the beginning and at the end of the training session.

The collected data was analyzed by using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics was used to estimate the frequency and percentages of demographic data. Chi-square test was used to assess the association between study variables. The $p < 0.05$ was considered as statistically significant.

Results

Table 1: Clinicodemographic data of study participants.

Demographic data	Group IMT (n=40)		Group PMT (n=40)	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Age (In years)				
31-40	05	12.5%	03	7.5%
41-50	14	35%	15	37.5%
51-60	14	35%	14	35%
Above 60	07	17.5%	08	20%
Gender				
Male	28	70%	24	60%
Female	12	30%	16	40%
Smoking status				
Yes	30	75%	33	82.5%
No	10	25%	07	17.5%

Table 2: Comparison of study parameter among both study groups.

Parameters	Group IMT		p-value	Group PMT		p-value
	Baseline	After session		Baseline	After session	
	Mean±SD	Mean±SD		Mean±SD	Mean±SD	
BMI (kg/m ²)	24.4±1.9	24.3±1.9	0.001	22.9±2.3	22.6±2.1	0.001
mMRC dyspnea scores	2.2±1.0	1.7±0.8	0.001	2.1±0.8	1.5±0.6	0.001
COPD assessment test score	24±6	17±4	0.027	22±5	16±3	0.042
6 minutes walking distance	418.6±64.2	439.2±67.1	0.982	427.5±66.1	467.2±65.17	0.528
SPO ₂	97.6±4.37	98.22±4.79	0.030	96.89±3.68	97.37±4.12	0.026
FEV ₁	50±8.98	51±9.18	0.0547	45.8±7.88	46.5±7.67	0.027

Discussion

Majority study participants were between age group 41-50 years followed by 51-60 years. The male participants were commonly observed in both groups. 75% of cases in group IMT and 82.5% of cases in group PMT were smokers (Table 1). A study by Buran Cirak *et al.*, found mean BMI 25.9 kg/m² and 26.4 kg/m² in IMT with MT and IMT only groups. Majority are male participants (80% in group IMT & MT and 83.3% in IMT only) [9]. Cheng *et al.*, included cases with mean age of 67.23 years and BMI of 23.02 kg/m² [10].

The mean BMI was 24.4 kg/m² and 24.3 kg/m² in group IMT and 22.9 kg/m² and 22.6 kg/m² in group PMT at baseline and after sessions respectively. The mean difference was statistically significant (p<0.05). The mMRC dyspnea scores are 2.2 and 1.7 in group IMT and 2.1 and 1.5 in group PMT at baseline and after sessions respectively. The COPD assessment test score was 24 at baseline and 17 after session in group IMT. Whereas, scores were 22 and 16 in group PMT at baseline and after sessions respectively. The mean difference of mMRC

dyspnea scores and COPD assessment test scores were statistically significant between two study groups. The mean 6 minutes walking distance showed increase from baseline to end of sessions. However, the mean difference was statistically not significant ($p>0.05$). There was a significant improvement in the mean oxygen saturation levels in group IMT and PMT from baseline ($p<0.05$). The mean FEV₁ was 50 ± 8.98 and 51 ± 9.18 in group IMT and 45.8 ± 7.88 and 46.5 ± 7.67 in group PMT. The mean difference was statistically significant in group PMT ($p<0.05$) (Table 2). A Systemic review and meta-analysis by Figueiredo *et al.*, reported that the comparison between IMT and control groups showed an improvement in FEV₁. The 6 minutes walking distance showed significant improvement in the isolated IMT, especially in cases without respiratory muscle weakness. The quality of life and dyspnea was statistically not significant ($p<0.05$) [11]. Smart *et al.* (2013) and Charususin *et al.* (2013) reported that in addition to increasing respiratory muscle strength, inspiratory muscle training improved functional capacity, quality of life, dyspnoea and exercise capacity [12,13]. de Medeiros *et al.*, observed improvement in the functional capacity assessed by the six minutes' walk test (MD 80 m, 95% CI 41 to 119) and FVC (MD 0.70 litres, 95% CI 0.53 to 0.87). In addition, breathing exercise showed significant effect on FEV₁ [14]. Gosselink *et al.*, reported that IMT improves inspiratory muscle strength and endurance, functional exercise capacity, dyspnoea and quality of life [15].

A study by Buran Cirak *et al.*, found improvement in the FEV₁ and FVC values were improved with the addition of MT to IMT [9]. Cheng *et al.*, reported that the mean FEV₁ was 40.05 and 43.75 before and after respiratory muscle training. The comparison of RMT training effect between severities of

FEV₁ in patients with COPD showed improved FEV₁ (46.32 in IMT only and 41.43 in IMT with EMT), CAT score (7.75 in IMT only and 10.00 in IMT with EMT), mMRC score (1.20 in IMT only and 1.07 in IMT with EMT) and distance of 6MWT (321.75 in IMT only and 351.92 in IMT with EMT). The mean difference of FEV₁ (%), CAT score, mMRC score and distance of 6MWT are statistically not significant ($p>0.05$) (10). The present study has limitations in terms of number of participants and lack of control group. The IMT and PMT were conducted and compared separately instead together.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the inspiratory muscle training and peripheral muscle training are similarly effective in progressing severity of dyspnea, exercise capacity, COPD assessment test score, and quality of life in cases with moderate to severe COPD. However, there was no significant progress in the lung function was apparent.

References

1. Global Strategy for the Diagnosis, Management and Prevention of COPD. Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD) 2017. Available at: <http://goldcopd.org>. Accessed on June 1, 2018.
2. Heijdra YF, Dekhuijzen PN, Van Herwaarden CL, *et al.* Nocturnal saturation and respiratory muscle function in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Thorax* 1995; 50: 610–612.
3. Gosselink R, Troosters T, Decramer M. Peripheral muscle weakness contributes to exercise limitation in COPD. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* 1996; 153: 976–980.
4. O'Donnell DE, Travers J, Webb KA, *et al.* Reliability of ventilatory parameters during cycle ergometry in multicentre

- trials in COPD. *Eur Respir J* 2009; 34:866–74.
5. Lacasse Y, Martin S, Lasserson TJ, *et al.* Meta-analysis of respiratory rehabilitation in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. A Cochrane systematic review. *Eura Medicophys* 2007; 43:475–85.
 6. Dellweg D, Reissig K, Hoehn E, Siemon K, Haidl P. Inspiratory muscle training during rehabilitation in successfully weaned hypercapnic patients with COPD. *Respir Med* 2017; 123:116-123.
 7. Borge CR, Hagen KB, Mengshoel AM, *et al.* Effects of controlled breathing exercises and respiratory muscle training in people with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: results from evaluating the quality of evidence in systematic reviews. *Bmc Pulm Med* 2014; 14:184.
 8. Ries AL, Bauldoff GS, Carlin BW. Pulmonary rehabilitation: joint ACCP/AACVPR evidence-based clinical practice guidelines. *Chest* 131: 2007; 4-42.
 9. Buran Cirak Y, Yilmaz Yelvar GD, Durustkan Elbasi N. Effectiveness of 12-week inspiratory muscle training with manual therapy in patients with COPD: A randomized controlled study. *Clin Respir J*. 2022 Apr;16(4):317-328.
 10. Cheng YY, Lin SY, Hsu CY, Fu PK. Respiratory Muscle Training Can Improve Cognition, Lung Function, and Diaphragmatic Thickness Fraction in Male and Non-Obese Patients with Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease: A Prospective Study. *J Pers Med*. 2022 Mar 16;12(3):475.
 11. Figueiredo RIN, Azambuja AM, Cureau FV, Sbruzzi G. Inspiratory Muscle Training in COPD. *Respir Care*. 2020 Aug;65(8):1189-1201.
 12. Smart NA, Giallauria F, Dieberg G. Efficacy of inspiratory muscle training in chronic heart failure patients: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Int J Cardiol*. 2013; 167:1502–1507.
 13. Charususin N, Gosselink R, Decramer M, McConnell A, Saey D, Maltais F. Inspiratory muscle training protocol for patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (IMTCO study): a multicentre randomised controlled trial. *BMJ Open*. 2013;3: e003101.
 14. de Medeiros AIC, Fuzari HKB, Rattesa C, Brandão DC, de Melo Marinho PÉ. Inspiratory muscle training improves respiratory muscle strength, functional capacity and quality of life in patients with chronic kidney disease: a systematic review. *J Physiother*. 2017 Apr;63(2):76-83.
 15. Gosselink R, De Vos J, van den Heuvel SP, Segers J, Decramer M, Kwakkel G. Impact of inspiratory muscle training in patients with COPD: what is the evidence? *Eur Respir J*. 2011 Feb; 37(2): 416-25.